

SUPPLEMENT 2. Information of the collections used for Phylogenies 1 and 2. Those collections sequenced in this study are in bold. Unavailable items are indicated with -. Holotypes, paratypes and epitypes are indicated by HT, PT and ET, respectively; note that the paratypes of a species are only indicated when its holotype is not present. For Phylogeny 1, the ITS, nrLSU, *tef1- α* and *β -tub* sequences of those collections without * are included. For Phylogeny 2, the ITS sequences of all collections are included.

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>tef1-α</i>	<i>β-tub</i>	
Ingroup								
<i>Britzelmayria</i>	<i>B. multipedata</i>	LO23704	Sweden	KC992888	KC992888	KJ732777	KJ664867	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	<i>B. supernula</i>	LO25004	Sweden	KC992867	KC992867	KJ732763	KJ664849	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
<i>Candolleomyces</i>	<i>Cd. brunneovagabundus</i>	L23204 (PT)	China	OR711043	OR711059	OR727287	OR727290	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2023)
	<i>Cd. incanus</i>	BJTCZ777 (HT)	China	ON042759	ON042766	ON098508	ON098513	Zhou <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>Cd. leucotephrus</i>	LO13801	Sweden	KC992885	KC992885	KJ732775	KJ664865	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	<i>Cd. singeri</i>	HMJAU37877	Sweden	MW301073	MW301091	MW314080	MW314062	Bau & Yan (2021b)
	<i>Cd. subminutisporus</i>	HMJAU37801 (HT)	China	MW301066	MW301094	MW314083	MW314065	Bau & Yan (2021b)
	<i>Cd. typhae</i>	LO2104	Sweden	DQ389721	DQ389721	KJ732776	KJ664866	Larsson & Örstadius (2008)
<i>Cantonopsathyra</i>	<i>Cn. serendipita</i>	HKAS145964 (HT)	China	PV155171	PV147345	PV156691	PV156729	This study
	<i>Cn. serendipita</i>	HTBM1626	China	PV155173	PV147347	PV156692	PV156730	This study
	<i>Cn. serendipita</i>	HTBM1177	China	PV155172	PV147346	-	-	This study
	<i>Cn. serendipita</i>	*HTBM2013	China	PV155168	-	-	-	This study
	<i>Cn. serendipita</i>	*HTBM2014	China	PV155169	-	-	-	This study
	<i>Cn. serendipita</i>	*HTBM2016	China	PV155170	-	-	-	This study
<i>"Ps." nigeriensis</i> clade	<i>"Ps." nigeriensis</i>	*K(M)7771 (HT)	Nigeria	MW491397	-	-	-	Direct submission by Eberhardt <i>et al.</i>
	<i>"Ps." nigeriensis</i>	*K(M)16759	Nigeria	MW491394	-	-	-	Direct submission by Eberhardt <i>et al.</i>
	<i>"Ps." nigeriensis</i>	*K(M)18624	Nigeria	MW491396	-	-	-	Direct submission by Eberhardt <i>et al.</i>
	<i>"Ps." nigeriensis</i>	*K(M)18635	Nigeria	MW491395	-	-	-	Direct submission by Eberhardt <i>et al.</i>
<i>Coprinellus</i>	<i>Co. aureogranulatus</i>	CBS97395	Unknown	GQ249274	GQ249283	GQ249267	GQ249258	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Co. curtus</i>	NL2339	Hungary	FM878016	FM876273	FM897246	FN396281	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2010 & 2011)
	<i>Co. deminutus</i>	NL0761	Unknown	JN159572	JN159592	-	JN159636	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2012)
	<i>Co. disseminatus</i>	NL2337	Hungary	FM878017	FM876274	-	FN396282	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2010 & 2011)
	<i>Co. domesticus</i>	NL1292	Unknown	FN396102	HQ847132	FM897229	FN396330	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Coprinopsis</i>	<i>Cp. atramentaria</i>	NL4245	Unknown	FN396123	FN396172	FN396225	FN396347	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Cp. calospora</i>	CBS61291 (HT)	Netherlands	GQ249275	GQ249284	GQ249268	GQ249259	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Cp. candidolanata</i>	NL2338	Norway	JN943137	JQ045873	FM897251	FN396273	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Cp. sclerotiger</i>	CBS59680	Unknown	GQ249277	GQ249286	GQ249269	GQ249261	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Cp. semitalis</i>	CBS29177 (HT)	UK	GQ249278	GQ249287	GQ249270	GQ249262	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Cp. udicola</i>	AM1240 (HT)	Germany	KC992967	KC992967	KJ732831	KJ664922	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Cp. vermiculifer</i>	CBS13246	Unknown	GQ249279	GQ249288	GQ249271	GQ249263	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Cystoagaricus</i>	<i>Cy. hirtosquamulosa</i>	Ramsholm800927	Unknown	KC992945	KC992945	-	-	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	<i>Cy. olivaceogrisea</i>	WK815635 (HT)	USA	KC992948	KC992948	-	-	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	<i>Cy. silvestris</i>	LO19192	Unknown	KC992949	KC992949	-	-	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
<i>Ephemerocybe</i>	<i>E. ephemera</i>	CBS184.51	Denmark	MH856804	MH868321	-	-	Vu <i>et al.</i> (2019)
	<i>E. callina</i>	NL1931	Unknown	FN396105	FN396158	FN396213	FN396299	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>E. cinereopallida</i>	NL0177 (HT)	Hungary	HQ847001	HQ847090	-	HQ847149	Direct submission by Nagy <i>et al.</i>
	<i>E. hiascens</i>	NL2536	Sweden	FM878018	FM876275	FM897253	FN396284	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2010 & 2011)

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SUPPLEMENT 2. (continued)

Genera	Species	Collections	Origins	GenBank Accession Nos.				References
				ITS	nrLSU	<i>tef-1a</i>	β - <i>tub</i>	
	<i>E. fuscocystidiata</i>	NL2720 (HT)	Norway	HQ846977	HQ847064	-	HQ847152	Direct submission by Nagy <i>et al.</i>
<i>Hausknechtia</i>	<i>Ha. floriformis</i>	WUJ22833 (HT)	Vanuatu	JX968254	JX968371	JX968458	-	Tóth <i>et al.</i> (2013)
	<i>Ha. leucosticta</i>	HFJAU1486 (ET)	China	OL435561	OL435565	OL439896	ON677539	Nie <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>Heteropsathyrella</i>	<i>He. macrocystidia</i>	HMJAU37802 (HT)	China	MW405102	MW413359	MW411004	MW410997	Bau & Yan (2021a)
	<i>He. macrocystidia</i>	HMJAU37803	China	MW405101	MW413358	MW411003	-	Bau & Yan (2021a)
<i>Homophron</i>	<i>Ho. camptopodum</i>	1997956	Unknown	KC992956	KC992956	-	-	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	<i>Ho. cernuum</i>	LO13498	Sweden	DQ389726	DQ389726	KJ732828	KJ664915	Larsson & Örstadius (2008)
	<i>Ho. spadiceum</i>	NL3996	Unknown	FN396132	FN396180	FN396231	FN396333	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Iugisporipsathyra</i>	<i>I. reticulopilea</i>	HFJAU1352 (HT)	China	ON207138	ON207137	-	ON210974	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>I. reticulopilea</i>	HFJAU3181	China	ON207139	-	-	ON210975	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2022)
<i>Kauffmania</i>	<i>K. larga</i>	LO22390	Sweden	DQ389694	DQ389694	KJ732824	KJ664912	Larsson & Örstadius (2008)
	<i>K. larga</i>	LAS97054	Sweden	DQ389695	DQ389695	-	-	Larsson & Örstadius (2008)
" <i>Lacrymaria</i> "	" <i>Lm.</i> " <i>glareosa</i>	LAS06019	Unknown	KC992954	KC992954	KJ732827	KJ664914	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	" <i>Lm.</i> " <i>hypertropicalis</i>	Guzman29585 (HT)	Mexico	KC992958	KC992958	-	KJ664916	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	" <i>Lm.</i> " <i>subcinnamomea</i>	Smith16957 (HT)	USA	KC992951	KC992951	-	-	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
<i>Narcissea</i>	<i>N. cordispora</i>	SFSUDEH2073	USA	AY461827	-	-	-	Keirle <i>et al.</i> (2004)
	<i>N. ephemeriodes</i>	HMJAU46343	China	MW832859	OL375252	-	-	Zhu <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	<i>N. patouillardii</i>	NL1687	Hungary	FM878009	FM876265	FM897238	FN396257	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Olotia</i>	<i>O. codinae</i>	GLMF112430 (HT)	Spain	MG696611	MG674714	-	-	Wächter & Melzer (2020)
<i>Parasola</i>	<i>Pa. auricoma</i>	NL0087	Hungary	JN943107	JQ045871	FM897236	FN396252	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009 & 2011)
	<i>Pa. conopilus</i>	NL0285	Hungary	FM163225	FM160684	FM897237	FN396247	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009 & 2011)
	<i>Pa. lilatincta</i>	NL0660	Hungary	FM163195	FM160714	FM897230	FN396246	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009 & 2011)
	<i>Pa. misera</i>	NL0677	Hungary	FM163211	FM160698	FM897240	FN396249	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009 & 2011)
	<i>Pa. plicatilis</i>	NL0295	Hungary	FM163216	FM160693	FM897242	FN396253	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2009 & 2011)
<i>Psathyrella</i>	<i>Ps. arenosa</i>	LO22096 (HT)	Sweden	KC992895	KC992895	KJ732784	KJ664875	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Ps. lyckebodensis</i>	LO30111 (HT)	Sweden	KC992921	KC992921	KJ732804	KJ664894	Örstadius <i>et al.</i> (2015)
	<i>Ps. maculata</i>	CBS20633	Unknown	GQ249281	GQ249290	GQ249273	GQ249265	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	<i>Ps. sacchariolens</i>	NL3995	Unknown	FN396133	FN396182	FN396233	FN396331	Nagy <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Punjabia</i>	<i>Pu. pakistanica</i>	MEL2382843	Australia	KP012718	KP012718	-	-	Direct submission by Bonito <i>et al.</i>
	<i>Pu. pakistanica</i>	LAH35323 (HT)	Pakistan	MH366736	-	-	-	Hussain <i>et al.</i> (2018)
<i>Typhrasa</i>	<i>Ty. gossypina</i>	Schumacher024	Unknown	KC992946	KC992946	KJ732825	-	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	<i>Ty. nanispora</i>	Barta980706 (HT)	Austria	KC992947	KC992947	-	-	Direct submission by Larsson & Örstadius
	<i>Ty. polycystis</i>	HFJAU1454 (HT)	China	MW466538	MW466544	MW475280	-	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2021)
	<i>Ty. rugocephala</i>	HFJAU1467 (HT)	China	MW466541	MW466546	MW475282	-	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Outgroup								
<i>Laccaria</i>	<i>Lc. sp.</i>	ZRL20151663	Unknown	LT716039	KY418855	KY419058	-	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2017)